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Objet : Report on JpGU-AGU Joint Meeting in Chiba and on the field trip to the Itoigawa-Shizuoka Fault Line in Japan (may 2017)

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1 Context

Since the beginning of the SURface RUpture due to Earthquakes (SURE) Database project, launched by IRSN in 2015, three workshops have been organized: one in Paris in 2015, the kick-off meeting, one in Menlo Park, California in December 2016 as well as a session in San Francisco, California at the AGU Fall Meeting 2016.

Thanks to these previous initiatives, I was invited in May 2017 by Koji Okumura (KO) (Hiroshima University) and Takashi Azuma (TA) (AIST, Geological Survey of Japan) to co-convene a session on Surface ruptures.

With KO, we took advantage of this occasion to spend two days in the field and to visit the “remnants” of the 2014 M6.2 Nagano Province earthquake surface rupture, as well as neotectonic and paleoseismological evidences along the same fault system (Itoigawa-Shizuoka Tectonic Line). I had also a meeting with the AIST-GSJ team (TA) in Tsukuba.

With TA, we decided to cooperate in order to include as much as possible Japanese cases in the SURE database (e.g. 2014 M6.2 Nagano Pref., 2011 and 2016 M5.5-6 Ibaraki Pref., 2016 Kumamoto earthquakes).

2 JpGU-AGU Joint Meeting - 20-25 May, 2017

For the 2017 joint JpGU-AGU meeting, together with TA (from AIST, Japan Geological Survey) and KO (from University of Hiroshima), both members of the TERPRO Commission - Earthquake Geology Focus Group, we co-organized a session dedicated to « **Surface ruptures during earthquakes : mapping, analyses, hazard assessment** ». This session took place on Wednesday 24th in the International Conference Hall of the Makuhari Messe conference center of Chiba, Japan.

The proposal for the session was as follows:

“The surface ruptures during earthquakes are invaluable information on the subterranean slip and rupture process. Recent progress in image analyses and laser scanning techniques innovated high-resolution three-dimensional mapping of the ruptures. We firstly examine the high-precision mapping of recent and past surface ruptures and discuss about the way to develop the technique. Secondly, the relationship of the earthquake source processes, strong motion generation, and geologic structure with observed surface deformation is an important unsolved issue. We still do not know much about correlation of slip at depth with slip at surface and about generation of seismic waves above seismogenic zone. Fault displacement hazard assessment is a new challenging technique that follows far behind the vibratory seismic hazard assessment of strong ground motions. Ongoing development of the fault displacement hazard assessment will be discussed together with the surface rupture database of past earthquakes.”

The session gathered 17 oral contributions and 13 posters, covering several topics in the themes of the sessions. Study cases were dominated by Japanese earthquakes, with 2016 Kumamoto on top!

Some other interesting cases were shown (2011 and 2016 brother earthquakes of Ibaraki province,

2014 Nagano earthquake, 2016 Norcia sequence in Italy, etc). There were also “methodological” contributions on fault displacement hazard. Several talks/posters focused on a peculiar topic related to surface rupture: “amplification” (or not) of shaking in the close vicinity of the rupture.

The session was originally aimed at gathering earthquake geologists from all over south-eastern Asia (Philippines, Myanmar, Indonesia, China, Taiwan, etc) where recent events with surface ruptures are numerous but description in the literature is scarce. From this point of view, this was not a success because most of the contributions treated Japanese cases or methodological issues.

Oral contributions:

- 1) Koji Okumura: **Introduction to the session on the surface ruptures during earthquakes**
- 2) Stéphane Baize, Johann Champenois, Francesca Cinti, Timothy Dawson, Yann Klingner, James McCalpin, Koji Okumura, David Schwartz, Oona Scotti, Pilar Villamor: **Towards a unified and worldwide database of surface ruptures (SURE) for Fault Displacement Hazard Analyses**
- 3) Lia Joyce Lajoie, Edwin Nissen, Chelsea Phillips Scott, J Ramon Arrowsmith, Tadashi Maruyama, Tatsuro Chiba, James Hollingsworth: **Surface rupture characteristics of the 2016 Kumamoto earthquake from correlation of lidar topography**
- 4) Sakae Mukoyama, takumi sato, tomoyuki takami: **Estimation of ground displacements around Aso-Caldera caused by the 2016 Kumamoto Earthquake, with the differential LiDAR DEM analysis**
- 5) Shinji Toda, Daisuke Ishimura: **Clues to evaluate short active fault learnt from the 2016 Kumamoto and Ibarakiken-hokubu, Japan, earthquakes**
- 6) Takao Kagawa, Shohei Yoshida, Hiroshi Ueno: **Ground Motion Characteristics in the Vicinity of Surface Fault Ruptures due to the 2016 Kumamoto Earthquake**
- 7) Dan Kazuo, Kiyoshi Irie, Saruul Dorjpalam, Torita Haruhiko: **Proposal of Evaluation Method of Strong Ground Motions in Area Close to the Fault Trace**
- 8) Tadashi Narabayashi: **Development Risk Evaluation Methods and Measures for Fault Movement by Engineering Approach**
- 9) Yoshikazu Suzuki, Makoto Takao, Koji Okumura, Kazuo Tani: **Fault displacement hazard analysis for risk evaluation**
- 10) Makoto Takao, Satoshi Kaneko, Tetsushi Kurita: **Study on occurrence probability of distributed faults in PFDHA**
- 11) Takashi Azuma: **Occurrence ratio of estimated fault displacement along active faults**
- 12) Yoshinobu Tsuji: **High density distributions of victims of inland earthquakes in the vicinity of the faults**
- 13) Shinichi Matsushima: **Surface Rupture and Structural Damage**
- 14) Yuichi S. Hayakawa, Shigekazu Kusumoto, Nobuhisa Matsuta: **Earthquake-induced surface deformations in a small mud volcano: multi-temporal high-definition measurements using TLS and UAS-SfM**
- 15) ~~Asdani Soehaimi: **ACTIVE FAULT AND SURFACE RUPTURES OF PIDIE EARTHQUAKE ON 7th DECEMBER 2016, ACEH, INDONESIA**~~ cancelled
- 16) CAGIL KARAKAS, Paul Tapponnier, Soma Nath Sapkota, Paramesh Banerjee, Sorvigenaleon Ildefonso, Laurent Bollinger, Yann Klingner, Magali Rizza, Aurelie Coudurier Curveur: **Imaging the seismic history of the MFT: a 100km-long Airborne Lidar Survey in Eastern Nepal**

- 17) Aurelie Coudurier Curveur, Elise Kali, Paul Tapponnier, Jerome van der Woerd, Swapnamita Choudhury, Saurabh Baruah, Cagil Karakas, Paramesh Banerjee, Sorvigenaleon Ildefonso, Emile Okal: **Surface ruptures of great (M>8) earthquakes in Eastern Himalayas: characteristic slip over the last 9ky**

Posters:

- 1) Ling-Ho Chung, Ray Y Chuang, J Bruce H Shyu, Mong-Han Huang, Kenn-Ming Yang, Kuo-En Ching, Yuan-Hsi Lee: **Shallow crustal structures triggered by the ML6.6 Meinong earthquake, southwestern Taiwan, from field investigation of surface deformation and damages**
- 2) Hiroshi Une, Takayuki Nakano, Satoshi Fujiwara, Tomokazu Kobayashi, Yu Morishita, Kazumi Iwata, Hiroshi P. Sato, Hiroshi YAGI: **Field survey and interpretation of the surface linear ruptures in northwest of the outer rim of the Aso caldera emerged on SAR interferogram**
- 3) Tatsuro Chiba, kazuo oda, kazuya funakoshi, toko takayama: **Surface rupture characteristics of the 2016 Kumamoto earthquake from compare of LiDAR DEM**
- 4) Chengli LIU, Yong ZHENG, Zujun XIE, Xiong XIONG: **Rupture features of the 2016 Mw6.2 Norcia earthquake and its possible relationship with strong seismic hazards**
- 5) Maxwell Wilkinson, Laura Gregory, Richard Walters, Luke Wedmore, Ken McCaffrey, Richard Jones, Gerald Roberts, Robert Holdsworth: **An example of slip on a capable fault: Near-field co-seismic deformation of the 30th October Central Italy earthquake (6.6 Mw) measured using low-cost GNSS**
- 6) Ken Xiansheng Hao, David Barrell, Mark Stirling, Katrina Sauer, Jack Williams, Grace Duke: **Co-seismic offsets and damage associated with the Hundalee Fault during the 2016 Kaikoura, New Zealand, M7.8 earthquake**
- 7) TAKUMI ONUMA: **Satellite SAR differential interferometry analysis on surface deformation associated with 2011 and 2016 earthquakes in northern part of Ibaraki prefecture**
- 8) Yasuo Awata, Takashi Azuma, Tadashi Maruyama: **Recurrence of similar surface ruptures associated with the M 6 earthquakes of 2011 and 2016, northern Ibaraki, Japan**
- 9) Keitaro Komura, Koutaro Aiyama, Keiichi Ueta, Yasuhira Aoyagi, Toshinori Sasaki, Takahiro Nagata, Kazuo Kobori: **Preliminary report of co-seismic surface rupture produced by the 28 December 2016 Hokubu-Ibaraki earthquake, northern Kanto region, Japan.**
- 10) Naoko Kitada, Naoto Inoue, Masao Tonagi: **Study on the Evaluation Method for Fault Displacement: Probabilistic Approach Based on Japanese Earthquake Rupture Data - Principal fault displacements along the fault**
- 11) Naoto Inoue, Naoko Kitada, Takashi Kumamoto: **Evaluation of earthquake source fault length from active fault and subsurface information**
- 12) Naoto Inoue, Naoko Kitada, Yasuhiro Matsumoto, Tsutomu Takahama, Tonagi Masao, Luis Angel Dalguer, Kojiro Irikura: **Investigation of off-fault displacement**
- 13) Tonagi Masao, Tsutomu Takahama, Yasuhiro Matsumoto, Naoto Inoue, Kojiro Irikura, Luis Angel Dalguer: **Study on the evaluation method for fault displacement: Deterministic evaluation approach based three step considerations**

Besides this session, I could attend other interesting sessions. I just report here some of them:

- “Active faults and paleoseismology” (S-SS12) : most of the talks were focused on the active faults responsible for the 2016 Kumamoto sequence, including their earthquake history or the 2016 Kumamoto surface deformation (including post-seismic)
- “Crustal Deformation” (S-SS10) encompasses talks dealing with geodesy as a tool to understand crustal deformation due to earthquakes, volcanic processes,
- “Subduction zone dynamics” (S-SS04) with many talks/posters on the M9 Tohoku earthquake and also on the Hikurangi subduction in New Zealand (e.g. slow slip events triggered by the crustal Kaikoura quake by L. Wallace)
- A session on “Histories of faults” (S-GL35) during which researchers presented the advances on dating the fault gouges
- A session on “Earthquake modelling and Simulation” (S-SS08) with a notable talk by R. Ando on Dynamic rupture simulation of the Kaikoura earthquake.

3 Meeting with the AIST-GSJ (26 may)

In Tsukuba facilities of AIST-GSJ, I had discussions with Takashi Azuma (TA) and colleagues on the availability of the data gathered by the geological survey (AIST-GSJ) and by other teams (from universities) and their potential transfer for the SURE Database.

A dataset related to the Kumamoto earthquake has already been published by the GSJ team in 2016. However, this could be completed with other measurements provided by University colleagues. To include these new data in the SURE database, we would have to wait for their publication. During the JpGU-AGU meeting, and especially during our session, several recent surface-rupturing earthquakes in Japan were presented and potentially could be included in SURE (e.g. the “twin” M6 earthquakes of Northern Ibaraki Prefecture in 2011 and 2016).

TA, member of the TERPRO committee, is a provider of data to the SURE Database. We planned to submit a JSPS proposal together with AIST-GSJ staff: the idea is to get funds for travels between Europe and Japan to develop the database.

4 2014 Field excursion on the Itoigawa-Shizuoka Tectonic Line, Central Japan (27-28 may)

The Itoigawa-Shizuoka Tectonic Line (Figure 1) is known as one of the largest and most active crustal fault zone in Japan (https://gbank.gsj.jp/activefault/index_e_gmap.html). This is also an important geological fault, because it separates two different crustal blocks. During the Mio-Pliocene times, the Central and Northern sections were East-dipping normal which controlled the accumulation of a thick series of Miocene-Pliocene sediments. During the Quaternary, this fault has been inverted with the westward displacement of the Eastern block to the West.

The ISTL is constituted of several structural segments. The northernmost one is the Kamishiro Fault which partly ruptured in 22/11/2014 (M6.2). South of the East Matsumoto Basin Fault (that we did not visit), the fastest in-land crustal fault of Japan (Gofukuji Fault) crosses the city of Matsumoto (population ≈ 250,000).

4.1 The 2014 M6.2 Nagano Prefecture earthquake surface rupture (2.5 y after)

We reached then the 2014 M6.2 earthquake surface rupture after a trip including 1.5 hours of train to Nagano city (Shinkansen line) and 1 hour of car from Nagano to Hakuba to the West.

The coseismic rupture, clearly breaking the surface, (Figure 2) is still visible in some spots despite the initial relatively small displacements (Figures 3 to 6) which have been partially erased by erosion. The surface rupture of this moderate magnitude event is somehow a curiosity for several reasons. First, the earthquake was caused by the break of a reverse fault which usually does not reach the surface for this range of magnitude. According to Takao et al. (2013), the probability of surface rupture for such an event is only of 20% in Japan.

Figure 1: General map of the Itoigawa-Shizuoka Tectonic Line, illustrating the different segments and the historical seismicity around (from Okumura 2001)

Second, the rupture re-emerged along the (almost) exact trace that was mapped before by geologists and, in addition, it occurred almost at the same place where Okumura (2001) evidenced 4 past surface rupturing earthquakes during the last 6 ka, including the historical event in 841 AD. Another interesting point is that this earthquake was significantly smaller than the characteristic earthquake (Okada et al., 2015) that could be "predicted" from the paleoseismic data gathered in trenches (see the information available in the National Database for the Kashimiro Fault (https://gbank.gsj.jp/activefault/index_e_gmap.html)).

Two years and a half after the earthquake, we were not especially optimistic when driving the alluvial plain of the powerful rivers of the Hakuba Basin. Nonetheless, we were able to distinguish some remnants in some places. The surface rupture was discontinuously mapped over 9 km from the Shiojima site to the north to Horinouchi site where Koji Okumura dug a (successful) trench in 1998. The reverse fault is running at the bottom of the mountain range which bounds the Hakuba valley to the east. Consistently with the cumulative relief, the earthquake fault uplifted the south-eastern block.

The Shiojima site is where the maximum co-seismic displacement was measured in 2014 (vertical throw: 90 cm) (Katsube et al., 2017). The vertical component of the rupture is still obvious and the rupture has even been preserved with a plastic coverage.

Several hundred meters to the east, a secondary rupture mapped after the quake (Katsube et al. 2017) can still be inferred in the field within the hanging wall: the rice paddy, a flat reference, seems bended with an emerging bump (red arrow), which corresponds with tension cracks on the concrete water pipe. This preservation would mean that the paddy was not re-arranged after the quake.

On Figure 7, the locations of the visited sites are reported, together with the table of slip measurements published by Katsube et al. (2017). This earthquake case is ready to be implemented in the SURE database.

Figure 2: A general view (to the south) of the scarp at waypoint Nagano1 just after the quake (November 2014). Provided by Koji Okumura

Figure 3: View of the same scarp as in Figure 2 (but opposite direction) in May 2017 (right). The fault scarp has been covered, so that the details of the rupture are preserved (left).

Figure 4: Remnants of a secondary antithetic rupture measured by Katsube et al. (2017). An abnormal “bump” in the rice paddy and a tensional crack on top of the water pipe (Waypoint Nagano2).

Figure 5: Waypoint Nagano4: the vertical bending of the lateral walls of the track reveals ~40 cm max. of synthetic

Figure 6: Waypoint Nagano8: oblique (reverse left-lateral) secondary rupture close to the southern end of the 2014 fault

Fig. 4. Detailed map of the distribution of the surface rupture and related surface deformation associated with the 2014 Nagano-ken Hokubu earthquake. Active fault traces are modified from Matsuta et al. (2006), and base maps are derived from 1:25,000 digital topographic maps published by the Geospatial Information Authority of Japan.

Nagano 1 - Synthetic scarp with 90 cm +
 Further SW: Fixed road with flexure scarp
 Nagano 2 - rice paddy seems flexured + drainage flexured with open
 cracks at anticline and closed cracks at syncline

Fig. 4. Continued.

Nagano 3 - pavement seems to be flexured/damaged with E uplifted.
 at the toe of cumulative scarp displacing the Holocene terrace
 Nagano 4 small synthetic rupture (flexure) around the cemetery, on the hanging
 wall.
 Nagano 5 Damaged house + paddy seems uplifted (1/2 dry, 1/2 wet)
 Nagano 6 Small vertical offset of road + LL component

Fig. 4. Continued.

Nagano 7 - Site of Kondo trench - w/ flexure map
 Nagano 8 - Site of Shuji Tachibana trench. Tear fault NW with LL component and N block uplifted.
 Nagano 9 - Trench Kaji 200A.

Table 1. Survey sites and slip measurements of the surface rupture associated with the 2014 Nagano-ken Hokubu earthquake.

Site	Fault strike	Trace ¹¹	Slip (cm) ¹²				Location	
			V	H	L	Total	Latitude	Longitude
NGH23		M	10			10	36° 42' 47.0" N	137° 52' 55.1" E
NGH22		P	4			4	36° 42' 45.0" N	137° 52' 59.0" E
NGH27	95	M	30	26		40	36° 42' 45.0" N	137° 52' 51.2" E
NGH21	260	P	20			20	36° 42' 41.4" N	137° 52' 57.5" E
NGH20	85	P	40			40	36° 42' 41.1" N	137° 52' 56.4" E
NGH24		P	20		20	20	36° 42' 40.0" N	137° 52' 51.0" E
NGH14	31	M	90			90	36° 42' 29.7" N	137° 52' 38.4" E
NGH53	51	B	20			20	36° 42' 28.7" N	137° 52' 58.6" E
NGH52		B	30			30	36° 42' 28.0" N	137° 52' 57.5" E
NGH51	26	B	40			40	36° 42' 26.4" N	137° 52' 56.6" E
NGH47		M	80			80	36° 42' 26.4" N	137° 52' 35.6" E
NGH50	21	B	50			50	36° 42' 24.9" N	137° 52' 55.9" E
NGH46		M	75			75	36° 42' 23.8" N	137° 52' 33.1" E
NGH49	30	B	60			60	36° 42' 23.3" N	137° 52' 54.8" E
NGH48	40	B	30			30	36° 42' 20.2" N	137° 52' 52.2" E
NGH54	20	B	40			40	36° 42' 10.6" N	137° 52' 47.6" E
NGH44	25	M	50			50	36° 42' 2.8" N	137° 52' 20.0" E
NGH13		M	40			40	36° 41' 50.0" N	137° 52' 11.4" E
NGH42	75	M	30	30		30	36° 41' 42.6" N	137° 52' 0.8" E
NGH40	40	M	20			20	36° 41' 41.5" N	137° 51' 54.9" E
NGH41	35	M	20			20	36° 41' 40.0" N	137° 51' 54.4" E
NGH39	30	M	15	15		21	36° 41' 34.5" N	137° 51' 49.8" E
NGH38	30	M	15	4	16	8	36° 41' 28.6" N	137° 51' 43.9" E
NGH32	20	M	8			8	36° 41' 15.4" N	137° 51' 37.7" E
NGH31	170	M	5			5	36° 41' 13.9" N	137° 51' 37.4" E
NGH16-2	20	M	30			30	36° 40' 14.6" N	137° 51' 8.3" E
NGH16	20	M	50			50	36° 40' 9.3" N	137° 51' 5.8" E
NGH15-2	20	M	50			50	36° 40' 0.1" N	137° 51' 5.3" E
NGH15	315	M	70			70	36° 40' 0.8" N	137° 51' 6.1" E
NGH12		M	60			60	36° 39' 48.0" N	137° 51' 6.5" E
NGH11	272	M	20	20		28	36° 39' 42.7" N	137° 51' 10.1" E
NGH37		M	2			2	36° 39' 34.4" N	137° 51' 12.8" E
NGH09		M	1			1	36° 39' 27.9" N	137° 51' 23.6" E
NGH35		M	5			5	36° 39' 27.6" N	137° 51' 16.0" E
NGH33	14	M	4			4	36° 39' 20.8" N	137° 51' 20.8" E
NGH34	14	M	12			12	36° 39' 20.6" N	137° 51' 21.3" E
NGH08		M	28			28	36° 39' 13.7" N	137° 51' 23.5" E
NGH07		M	5			5	36° 39' 6.9" N	137° 51' 28.8" E
NGH06	5	M	21			21	36° 39' 4.4" N	137° 51' 26.5" E
NGH05	61	M	2	2		3	36° 39' 4.0" N	137° 51' 31.3" E
NGH04		M	4			4	36° 38' 59.8" N	137° 51' 28.9" E
NGH19-2	65	M	10	15	18	18	36° 38' 47.4" N	137° 51' 40.3" E
NGH19	65	M	3	4	5	3	36° 38' 45.9" N	137° 51' 39.2" E

¹¹ Code of fault trace. M: main trace, B: back thrust trace, P: southeastern trace of pop-up.
¹² Type of measured slip. V: vertical slip, H: horizontal slip, L: lateral slip. Total slip is geometrically calculated as a net slip using different two types of slip data.

Figure 7: Surface rupture maps (with my own annotations) and slip measurements by Katsube et al. 2017

4.2 The Gofukuji fault, a very active fault in an urban area

The second day of our trip was focused on the Matsumoto area. Matsumoto is a large city (more than 240 000 inhabitants in 2010, according to Wikipedia). The city is built in the alluvial plain at the very edge of the rapid fault system, and this city can be considered under a real seismic threat (Figures 8 and 9). Koji Okumura performed several studies along the ISTL segments (including that close to Matsumoto, the Gofukuji segment), which are summarized in his paper in 2001 (Okumura, 2001).

Figure 8: An overview of Matsumoto city and its basin, bounded to the east by the East Matsumoto Basin Fault (EMBF) to the north and by the Gofukuji Fault to the south.

The historical catalogue of Japan provides scarce information on the events that hit and damaged the city. It seems that, according to archives, the GF ruptured the surface either in 762 AD or 841 AD, so a long time ago. According to geological evidences, on the other hand, the slip rate of the fault is very high, probably the highest of onshore crustal faults in Japan: 9 mm/a (Okumura, 2001).

The evidences of rapid tectonics are provided by displaced morphological features and analysis of several trenches (Figure 9). The first relevant site is located in the southern suburbs of Matsumoto (waypoints Matsu1 and Matsu2), called Namiyanagi in Okumura (2001). There, KO could map several terrace risers which have been left-laterally displaced. The left-lateral fault trace is remarkably marked at some places in the alluvial plain (Matsumoto) where it juxtaposes terraces of different ages (Figure 10).

Figure 9: General map (2A) of the Matsumoto area faults and focus on the trenched area (Namiyanagi) (2C) reported by Okumura (2001). Detailed map (2B) illustrates the morphological evidence of left-lateral offset of the T1 terrace riser (R2) in the same zone. From Okumura (2001).

According to the dates obtained for sediments of these terraces, Okumura (2001) came out with a very high slip rate (9 mm/a). Several trenches (Matsu1), confirming the occurrence of surface faults, have been dug in this zone which has since been extensively modified by human activity.

Figure 10: View of the fault in the urbanized area of Matsumoto. This picture was shot parallel to the fault strike (towards the north) (waypoint Matsu2).

A second interesting site was visited, several km to the south, the Nakayama pressure ridge-related scarp, where KO could infer a 100-150 m left-lateral deflection of an incised creek.

The counter-slope scarp marks the trace of the Gofukuji left-lateral fault (Figure 11), in the Nakayama area (top picture), with close-up of a potential site for future trenching (bottom-left). The map (bottom right), from Okumura (2006), provides an overview of the creek deflection (waypoint Matsu3).

Several trenches have been performed across this fault segment; however, future investigations could be carried out to complete the picture and update the results.

5 References

Katsube, A., et al. (2017). Surface rupture and slip associated with the 2014 Nagano-ken Kokubu earthquake (Mw6.2). *Journal Geological Society of Japan*, 123, 1-21 (abstract and figure captions in english).

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View of the scarp at the bottom of the pressure ridge

Figure 11: Illustration of the morphological imprint of the left-lateral Gofukuji Fault in the Nakayama area